

Synthesis of some New 3,5-Disubstituted-pyrazoles

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The synthesis of a few new 3,5-disubstituted-pyrazoles (2) having phenyl and substituted-phenyl moieties starting from 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds (1) have been described.

CHEMISTRY¹ and wide range pharmacological properties of pyrazoles have been cited in literature. In the present work an attempt has been made to synthesise some new 3,5-disubstituted-pyrazoles (2) by condensing different β -diketones (1) with hydrazine hydrate in alcoholic medium. (Scheme 1). The structure of the compounds have been established on the basis of their elemental analysis, nmr and ir spectral data. The ir spectra of the pyrazoles show band at 1610 (C=N)², 3435 (NH of pyrazole ring)³ and 3245 cm⁻¹ (OH phenolic).

Scheme 1

Experimental

β -Diketones (1): The compounds were prepared following the earlier methods⁴.

3-Phenyl-5-(3'-methyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-pyrazole (2a): To 1-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methylphenyl)-3-phenylpropan-1,3-dione (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (20 ml), hydrazine hydrate (25%, 5 ml) was added and refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured over cold water with stirring. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from suitable solvent to yield 2a (76%), m.p. 179° (Found: C, 76.1; H, 5.02; N, 10.7. Requires: C, 76.8; H, 5.6; N, 11.2%); δ 2.34 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 6.84–7.58 (10H, m, ArH, NH, =CH) and 10.82 (s, OH). Similarly, 2b–g were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF 3,5-DISUBSTITUTED-PYRAZOLES (2)*

Sl. no.**	R ₁	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	3-CH ₃ , 2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	179	76
2.	4-CH ₃ , 2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	177	68
3.	5-CH ₃ , 2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	159	70
4.	5-Br 2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	198	65
5.	3,4-(OH) ₂ , 2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	199	72
6.	3,5-Cl ₂ , 2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	222	74
7.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	179	68
8.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	129	50

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

**Compound Sl. nos. 1–6, R=phenyl; Sl. no. 7, 4-methoxyphenyl; Sl. no. 8, 4-nitrophenyl.

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